

uninoculated plot. The results support the idea of equating the presence of a distinct structural mode at high nematode populations with the outcome

of primary crop infestation at about the time of sowing. They also demonstrate the possibility of maintaining different levels of infestation in a single infested

tank despite biological continuity between the plots after the tank is flooded. ■

Pest management and control DISEASES

Effect of age of tungro-diseased plants on GLH infectivity

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The infectivity of the green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens* was determined by the test-tube inoculation method after feeding the insects on tungro-diseased TN1 plants of different ages. Diseased plants were inoculated 7 days after soaking, kept in the greenhouse for 15, 30, 60, and 90 days, and then used as virus sources for 1,920 adult GLH.

The percentages of infective insects varied among those fed on diseased plants

Infectivity of *Nephotettix virescens* fed on tungro-diseased TN1 plants of different ages, at various acquisition access times.^a

Diseased plant age (days)	Total (no.)	2h	24 h	96 h
Infective insects (%)				
15	480 insects	25 a	48 a	81 b
30	480 insects	55 b	82 b	90 c
60	480 insects	46 b	74 b	85 c
90	480 insects	20 a	29 a	62 a
Retention period (days)				
15	321 insects	1.2 a	1.4 a	1.8 b
30	345 insects	1.7 a	1.9 a	2.1 b
60	337 insects	1.7 a	1.9 a	1.8 b
90	363 insects	1.6 a	1.6 a	1.3 a
Infected seedlings (%)				
15	3,302 seedlings	5 a	9a	21 b
30	3,320 seedlings	13 a	20 a	28 c
60	3,304 seedlings	10 a	19 a	21 b
90	3,304 seedlings	5 a	6a	10 a

^aMeans followed by a common letter in each column are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Effect of tungro-infected source plants of different ages on percentage of rice green leafhoppers infective at acquisition access periods of 2,24, and 96 hours.

of different ages, regardless of acquisition access time (2, 24, or 96 hours) (see figure). At 96 hours access time, a higher percentage of the insects that fed on 30- and 60-day diseased plants became infective, had a longer infectivity retention period, and infected a greater

percentage of seedlings than the insects that fed on 15- or 90-day diseased plants (see table).

The variation in the insects' infectivity indicated that diseased plants of different ages were not identical in quality as virus sources. ■

Checking infection of rice root nematode by nursery treatment and bare root dips to increase yield

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Six pesticides — aldicarbsulfone, carbofuran, dimethoate, monocrotophos, phosphamidon, and quinalphos — were tested as bare root dip treatment for control of the rice root nematode

Hirschmanniella oryzae. Seedlings of the rice cultivar Triveni were raised in nursery beds treated with and without 30 liters DBCP/ha. They were transplanted in 4-m² microplots in the field after a 12-hour bare root dip in 0.02% pesticide solution. Each treatment was replicated three times.

Differences in nematode population between the check plots and the plots planted to seedlings that received both the DBCP treatment and the bare root dip with phosphamidon were significant. At planting, soil from plots with the treated seedlings had 202 nematodes, and soil from the check plots had 185. At harvest the former had 79 nematodes

and the latter, 273. At 35 days after transplanting the roots of treated seedlings had 4.7 nematodes/g root; the

roots in the check plots had 10.2 nematodes/g root. At harvest the former had 3 nematodes/plant and the

latter, 29/plant. Plots with the treated seedlings yielded 85% more than the check plots (1.5 kg vs 0.81 kg/plot). ■

Further studies on the potential of weeds to spread tungro in West Bengal, India

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In a previous study on the potential of weeds to spread rice tungro in West Bengal, no virus occurred naturally on the predominant graminaceous and cyperaceous weeds at the Kalyani virus experimental field. But *Echinochloa colona* and *Paspalum notatum* inoculated with the virus kept it for 3 months. In

a further study of weeds' potential for spreading rice tungro virus, weeds were collected from different locations early in different crop seasons.

The following weeds were collected in April 1978 and in June 1978: *Echinochloa colona*, *Paspalum notatum*, *Cynodon dactylon*, *Echinochloa crus-galli*, *Eleusine indica*, *Cyperus iria*, *Imperata cylindrica*, *Setaria glauca*, *Sporobolus diander*, *Cyperus esculentus*, *Leersia hexandra*, *Dicanthium annulatum*, *Brachiaria ramosa*, and *Dactyloctenium aegyptium*. Only *L. hexandra* was not obtained in June but another species,

Digitaria sanguinalis, was available. In November 1978 only nine weeds (*E. colona*, *C. dactylon*, *P. notatum*, *S. diander*, *C. esculentus*, *D. annulatum*, *I. cylindrica*, *B. Ramosa*, and *Cyperus rotundus*) were collected. None showed any virus except a few collections of *E. colona* from the endemic fields of Malda.

The weeds were then inoculated with the tungro virus and their retention of the virus was indexed on TN1 seedlings (see table). The research was funded by the Indian Council of Agricultural Research, New Delhi. ■

Transmission of rice tungro virus from weeds collected 2 to 5 months after inoculation, Kalyani, West Bengal, India, 1978.

Weed	Transmission (%)											
	April				June				November			
	2 mo	3 mo	4 mo	5 mo	2 mo	3 mo	4 mo	5 mo	2 mo	3 mo	4 mo	5 mo
<i>Echinochloa colona</i>	15	10	5	X	20	10	X	X	20	10	X	X
<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
<i>Eleusine indica</i>	X	X	X	X	25	15	10	X	X	X	X	X
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i>	X	X	X	X	X	Y	X	X	20	10	X	X
<i>Cyperus iria</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	X	X	X	X	10	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
<i>Imperata cylindrica</i>	X	X	X	X	20	10	X	X	X	X	X	X
<i>Paspalum notatum</i>	X	X	X	X	30	20	10	X	10	X	X	X
<i>Setaria glauca</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
<i>Sporobolus diander</i>	X	X	X	X	10	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
<i>Cyperus esculentus</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
<i>Leersia hexandra</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
<i>Dicanthium annulatum</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
<i>Brachiaria ramosa</i>	X	X	X	X	10	X	X	X	X	X	Y	X
<i>Dactyloctenium aegyptium</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
<i>Digitaria sanguinalis</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

1979 setback for ufra

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Ufra disease, caused by the rice stem nematode *Ditylenchus angustus* (Filipjev) is serious in deepwater rice in southern Bangladesh. It was particularly severe around the village of Kashimpur in Comilla district, almost at the northern limit of its distribution in southeastern

Bangladesh, according to disease surveys in November 1977 and 1978. In 1979, the disease disappeared from the area; no plants with symptoms were found during September. The average number of nematodes per stem in 6 fields about

80 m apart along a linear transect at Kashimpur was estimated using the procedure described by Cox and Rahman (IRRN 4[3] June 1979:10) at about the end of September (i.e. just before panicle initiation) in 1979 and in 1979 (see

Average number of nematodes per stem in 6 deepwater rice fields along a transect at Kashimpur, Bangladesh, 1978 and 1979.

Date	Sample size (stems/field)	Nematodes (av no./stem)						
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7
2 Oct 1978	15	- ^a	1421 ^b	9	49	786 ^{bc}	250	989 ^b
24 Sep 1979	50	4	- ^a	1	1	6	1	1

^aNo deepwater rice. ^bIncludes stems containing more than 3,000 nematodes. ^cThis crop was a total loss because of ufra in 1978.